

THE HISTORY AND CURRENT STATE OF PEDIATRIC TERMINOLOGY

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Annotation: Any person in his life is faced with special texts. The first of these, probably, are school textbooks, and subsequently we constantly deal with this kind of literature. A characteristic feature of a special text is the abundance of terms and vocabulary of a general scientific description. It seemed to us interesting to explore how different layers of vocabulary, terms from different areas of knowledge are related in the article, as well as to trace the cases of their use. The article deals with the history and current state of the terminology of pediatrics. The terminological system of pediatrics is represented by both general and specific linguo-conceptual characteristics. Emphasizes the contribution of well-known already-physicians in the formation of the terminology of this area of copper. The language of medicine is a reflection of scientific achievements and misconceptions of scientists from different historical periods.

Key words: history of science, term creation, pediatrics, scientific concept.

If we consider the terminology of pediatrics as a specific clinical discipline, then it is necessary, first of all, to note that for a long historical period it developed as a direct component of medical terminology. In the ancient set of median rules and instructions of China, "The Book of Mediain," there are a number of tips on the hygienic regimen of children, including recommendations on proper nutrition. Assistance during childbirth and childcare, especially newborns, was one of the oldest types of medical activity. The rudiments of obstetrics and pediatrics of early age arose historically together in a close inseparable connection. For all peoples, medical care for mother and child was in the hands of women who managed to accumulate considerable knowledge for that time and passed it on from generation to generation. The beginning of the "Doctrine of the Child" is usually attributed to the 4th century BC, by the time of writing the works: "On the seed and nature of the child", "On teething" by the father of medicine Hippocrates (460 - 377 BC). Hippocrates developed the doctrine of the diagnosis and semiotics of diseases. He laid the foundation for a

strictly consistent, systematic examination of the patient, using examination (examinatio), palpation (palpatio), percussion (percussio) and sloughing of the chest and abdomen (auscultatio), paid attention to the type of compartments, sediment in the urine, etc. He described many symptoms and syndromes. For example, in modern medical terminology, the term hippocratic splash zoom has been preserved. Sufficiently complete information about the medicine of Ancient Greece was obtained from the monuments of culture and literature.

First of all, it is necessary to name the poems "Iliad" and "Odyssey" by Homer. Homer mentions the power of the family of doctors, headed by Asclepius (in the Latin version, Aesculapius), later he was deified and exalted as the god of healing. Ancient Rome is the recipient of Greek and Oriental medicine. Speaking about the public side of medicine and hygiene, one cannot fail to note the high and well-organized order in the state. Even then, using the labor of slaves, water pipes (aqueducts), sewers (cesspools), baths (terms) were cooperating. Sanitary legislation was included in the so-called "Laws of the Twelve Tables". During the time of the Roman Republic (III-II century BC), doctors from Greece and Egypt, mostly slave doctors, appeared in the state. As the need for medical care grew, the authority of the doctor grew and free citizens began to work with them.

An enlightened man and wealthy slave owner Aulus Cornelius Celis (1st century BC - 1st century AD) became widely known in medicine. His work "De medicina" (On medicine) in 8 volumes is an encyclopedia of healing of that time. Celis, in particular, described 4 signs of inflammation: redness, swelling, pain, heat "Notae inflammationis sunt quattuor: rubor et tumor cum calore et dolore". The vocabulary of Celis's work "De medicina" with clarifications or word changes almost completely entered the dictionaries of modern medicine, for example: abdomen - stomach, cartilago - cartilage, cervix - zeya, cancer - cancer, hernia - hernia, papula - papule, etc. The largest doctor and the naturalist of Rome was Claudius Galen (129 - 201 AD) some historians of medicine find an incorrect attitude towards this folk experience in the field of child care. They argue that among primitive peoples, as well as in ancient historical periods, the attitude towards children's life and children's health was, as a rule, always dismissive. A great contribution to the development of the terminology of pediatrics was made by the followers and students of S.F. Khotoviekoy. Mikhail Samuilovich Zelenskoy is rightfully considered the first pediatric neurologist in Russia. His terminology, presented in the course of lectures "Diseases of the nervous system", is not outdated and is used in modern childhood neurology.

The outstanding Russian pediatrician Karl Andreevich Raukhfus (1835 - 1915) was the first Russian pediatric pathologist, otolaryngologist, pediatric cardiologist, reformer and organizer of pediatric patients and the education system for pediatric personnel. His name is immortalized in the term "Rauhfus triangle", denoting one of the signs of effusion pleurisy. Nikolai Petrovich Gundobin (1860 - 1907) outlined his vast scientific and practical experience in the fundamental work "Features of Childhood" (1906), which immediately entered the golden fund of world pediatrics and was a desktop guide for pediatricians for decades. N.P. Gundobin sacredly followed the commandment of Hippocrates "Medice, cura aegrotum, sed non morbum" (Enemy, lie down the patient, not the disease), in his book he writes: they treated diseases, and the patient himself was completely different. And in the latter circumstance lies the whole duty of the doctor and the clinic. The modern terminology of many areas, with all its verbal richness, contains few really terms - "general technical" and "industry". "A significant number of terms are multi-valued. Not only in different industries, but even within the same area, these terms either do not have a specific meaning, or have several meanings. In this regard, all terms can be divided into 5 groups:

- synonymous or plural terms;
- terms are polysemantic or polysemantic;
- terms are undifferentiated;
- descriptive terms.
- valid or unambiguous terms;

Conclusion:

The most inconvenient are the terms belonging to the 5th group. Their variety is extremely large. These include a significant number of expressions that do not even resemble a verbose term - these are simple descriptions that are given to the concept in dictionaries or textbooks. As an example, we can cite the concept from the field of aircraft control theory "method of approximation of the display of relative motion".

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